

Informed Consent

Feedback collection consent form

This form is provided through the NSF-supported EAGER: Secure Research Impact Metric Data Exchange: Data Supply Chain and Vocabulary Development grant (FAIN 2335827). It aims to collect stakeholder feedback on scholarship usage and impact related vocabularies aggregated across multiple sources. As you provide feedback in the form, you will need to reference two files:

- 1) Draft Glossary for Scholarship Usage and Impact Vocabularies
- 2) Draft Crosswalk for Scholarship Usage and Impact Vocabularies

Through this form, you can provide your feedback on a draft glossary and vocabularies crosswalk related to scholarship usage and impact metrics. The responses you provide will be aggregated and published without individual attribution or identification as a research dataset in the Zenodo Community affiliated with our project.

Completing this feedback form should take up to 10 minutes.

Questions about this research can be directed to
Principal Researcher Jennifer Kemp
at: jennifer@strategiesos.org
Project Principle Investigator Christina Drummond at:
christina.drummond@unt.edu

In clicking the button below to share your feedback, you acknowledge:

- Your participation is voluntary.
- You are 18 years or more of age.
- You may terminate your participation at any time for any reason by closing your browser window.
- Your feedback will be aggregated and published without identifying information within a research dataset.

- I consent to participate
 I do not wish to participate

Feedback form

This form is for collecting anonymous feedback on a draft glossary and crosswalk of key terms related to usage and impact across outputs and stakeholders. Please open and

review the following two files as you share your feedback:
Draft Glossary for Scholarship Usage and Impact Metrics:
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1jmBwGC1v9mMhaqu0L4TcQNdusp=sharing>

Draft Crosswalk for Scholarship Usage and Impact Metrics:
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1NkGk8Ky2KHlyMA8KtaARgInr3KUtfo/view?usp=sharing>

Overall, how well do you think the **glossary** represents key terms relating to scholarship use and impact across outputs and stakeholders?

Overall, how well do you think the **crosswalk** represents key terms relating to scholarship use and impact across outputs and stakeholders?

The **Glossary** and **Crosswalk** are meant to capture key terms related to scholarship usage and impact across output types. Please list here any key terms or sources that you think are missing.

A difficult term to define across stakeholders might be "open access." Do you have a source for a standard definition of "open access" that you use?

What is your source for a standard definition of "open access"?

In some cases, the **Crosswalk** includes very similar definitions. Is it useful for the **Crosswalk** to include multiple, similar definitions?

Please explain - for the **Crosswalk**, when are multiple similar definitions useful or not useful?

Should names and/or acronyms for organizations and efforts (e.g. ORCID, COUNTER, IDSA) be included in a scholarship usage and impact vocabularies **Glossary**?

Please explain - for a scholarship usage and impact vocabularies **Glossary**, when should an organization or effort be listed or not?

What, if any, organizations and efforts are missing from the scholarship usage and impact vocabularies **Glossary** that should be included?

If organizations and efforts are listed in the scholarship usage and impact vocabularies **Glossary** and/or **Crosswalk**, where should their definition come from? Please select all that apply

- The organization or effort itself (e.g. their website)
- References in peer efforts
- Other

The presentation format for the **Glossary** is being determined. Please rank the following formats in terms of usefulness for future Glossary use and reference.

	Not at all useful	Slightly useful	Moderately useful	Very useful	Extremely useful
Spreadsheet published to Zenodo	<input type="radio"/>				
Narrative document published in Zenodo	<input type="radio"/>				
Web-based dashboard, such as Tableau Public	<input type="radio"/>				
Peer reviewed publication	<input type="radio"/>				

The presentation format for the **Crosswalk** is being determined. Please rank the following formats in terms of usefulness for future **Crosswalk** use and reference.

	Not at all useful	Slightly useful	Moderately useful	Very useful	Extremely useful
Spreadsheet published to Zenodo	<input type="radio"/>				
Narrative document published in Zenodo	<input type="radio"/>				
Web-based dashboard, such as Tableau Public	<input type="radio"/>				
Peer reviewed publication	<input type="radio"/>				

Please share any other feedback on the proposed Glossary and Crosswalk for scholarship impact and usage metrics.